

Viscosity of Thorium Phosphate Gel-forming Mixtures during Gelation.

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Viscosity measurements have often been used for studying the processes involved in the formation of gels (cf. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 552). These measurements have been made during the gelation of gelatine solutions prepared under different conditions by Levites (*Z. Chem. Ind. Kolloide*, 1908, **2**, 208), Schroeder (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, **45**, 75), Gokun (*Kolloid Z.*, 1908, **3**, 84), Shoji (*Biochem. J.*, 1919, **13**, 227) and others who obtained smooth curves for the variation of the viscosity of these solutions with time. Levites found that the rate of increase of viscosity is nearly proportional to time while Shoji concluded that the viscosity-time curves in the early stage of gelation are represented by the equation

$$\eta - \eta_1 = \frac{\mu t}{1 + \frac{\mu t}{\lambda}}$$

where μ and λ are constants.

Mardles (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, **18**, 327) also found smooth viscosity-time curves during the gelation of a sol of cellulose acetate in benzyl alcohol and they could be represented by the formula,

$$\eta - \eta_0 = ae^{kt}$$

where η is the apparent viscosity of the gel-forming sol after an interval of time t , η_0 , the original viscosity of the sol, and k , the rate of gelation. Heymann (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, **31**, 846), however, found that the viscosity of methyl cellulose during the sol-gel transformation decreased with time regularly if the sol was aged at 44° but if the ageing took place at higher temperatures, the viscosity first decreased and then increased to a higher value.

Prakash and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 390) measured the viscosities of the gel-forming mixtures of various inorganic jellies during gelation and found that there are three distinct stages in the formation of gels. In the first stage there is very little change in viscosity with time and this corresponds to the passage of the crystal-

loidal substance to the colloidal state; in the second the regular exponential change in viscosity with time corresponds to the gradual neutralisation of the charge on the micelles with consequent increase in hydration; in the third stage there is a sudden rise in viscosity due to the formation of specific structures. Prasad, Mehta and Desai (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 1384) measured the viscosity during the formation of silicic acid gels and found that it increased regularly with time and that the viscosity-time curves were continuous. Their observations showed that the passage of crystalloidal silicic acid into colloidal state, the coagulation of colloidal silicic acid and the formation of specific structures form a single continuous process.

These authors (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 1391) also found that non-electrolytes accelerate the rate of change in viscosity of the alkaline mixtures while they retard that of the acidic ones and further that an increase in the amount of the non-electrolytes in the mixtures increases the acceleration or retardation of the rate of change in viscosity. Levites (*Z. Chem. Ind. Kolloide*, 1908, **2**, 237) observed that non-electrolytes retard the sol-gel transformation of gelatine and agar agar.

In the present investigation the viscosity of thorium phosphate gel-forming mixtures has been determined under different conditions during the progress of gelation. The effect of the variation of concentration of thorium nitrate and phosphoric acid as well as of the addition of electrolytes and non-electrolytes on the rate of change of viscosity has been examined.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The method as well as the apparatus used for measuring viscosity were those previously described by one of us (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 552; *Bom. Univ. J.*, 1935, **4**, 46).

Solutions of thorium nitrate and phosphoric acid were prepared from Kahlbaum's extra pure chemicals whose purity was tested before use. The concentrations of the solutions were 6% and 2*N*, respectively. A known amount of thorium nitrate solution was taken in a test tube and a known amount of the solution of phosphoric acid together with sufficient distilled water to make up the total volume of the mixture to 10 c.c. was taken in another test tube and the two were kept in a thermostat to attain a constant temperature. On mixing the two solutions a slight precipitate was obtained, which

disappeared on shaking the mixture. It was then introduced into the viscometer and suction at 15 cms. pressure of water, which was kept constant throughout the investigation, was applied. The gel-forming mixture remained transparent throughout the process of gelation.

The results obtained with mixtures containing different amounts of thorium nitrate and phosphoric acid are similar in nature. Only one of these results is shown in the following table in which η represents the viscosity at time T .

TABLE I.

Thorium nitrate = 0.48 g.		Phosphoric acid = 0.12 N.				
T	... 8' 27"	18' 47"	22' 51"	26'	31' 14"	42' 51"
$\eta \times 10^5$	... 1279	2223	2452	2816	3465	5076
T	... 49' 22"	57' 49"	72' 11"	82' 21"	96' 52"	
$\eta \times 10^5$	... 6198	7932	11470	13030	16240	

The viscosity of mixtures containing (i) a fixed amount of thorium nitrate and different amounts of phosphoric acid and (ii) fixed amount of phosphoric acid and different amounts of thorium nitrate, at different intervals of time is shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Effect of Non-electrolytes.—The effect of methyl, ethyl and *n*-propyl alcohols, acetone, glycol and glycerine on the viscosity of thorium phosphate gel-forming mixtures was investigated. Various quantities of these non-electrolytes were added to phosphoric acid solution to which sufficient distilled water was added to make the total volume of the gel-forming mixture 10 c.c. The nature of the results obtained is similar with all the non-electrolytes used, and is shown in Fig. 3 for ethyl alcohol which also shows the effect of the addition of increasing amounts of the non-electrolytes.

Effect of Electrolytes.—The effect of hydrochloric, nitric, sulphuric acids and of sodium chloride was investigated. The results with acids are shown in Fig 4 and those with sodium chloride in Fig. 5.

DISCUSSION.

It appears from the curves (Figs. 1 and 2) that after mixing the gel-forming constituents, the viscosity increases at first slowly for some time and later on the rate of increase becomes very rapid. The

continuous nature of the viscosity-time curves indicates that the colloidal particles in the mixture grow gradually to bigger dimensions and no sharp changes in their rate of aggregation and hydration take place during gelation. The three stages in the process of gel-formation found by Satya Prakash and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) from viscosity measurements are not obvious in the formation of thorium phosphate gels. Curves of $\log(\eta_s - \eta_0)$, where η_s and η_0 (η_0 refers to the extrapolated value of the viscosity from $\eta-t$ curves at 0 time) are the viscosities of the mixtures and water, respectively, plotted against $\log t$ (Fig. 6) from the curves of I, II, and III (Fig. 1) and IV and VII (Fig. 2) are straight lines with no breaks. This leads to the conclusion that the various stages involved in the setting of a gel, such as the formation of the colloidal particles, their hydration and coalescence and the acquiring of specific structures, altogether form one continuous process. It is important to note that the periodic nature of the viscosity-time curves obtained by previous workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 329, 589; 1934, 11, 173; 1935, 12, 552)

FIG. 1.

is not observed in the case of changes of viscosity of gel-forming mixtures. It is probable that the periodic or discontinuous nature of viscosity-time curves is to be expected only in the case of lyophobic sols or in those cases where sedimentation takes place.

With an increase in the amount of phosphoric acid, the rate of change in viscosity increases fairly rapidly as will be seen from the rapid increase in the steepness of the curves (Fig. 1). This may be due to an increase in (i) the number of micelles in unit volume or (ii) their size and their degree of hydration, or (iii) both. The first factor does increase as the amount of phosphoric acid in the gel-forming mixture is increased. But as all the mixtures were quite transparent after mixing and remained so till they set, there is no

FIG. 2.

direct evidence to show that the size of the micelles is considerably increased by increasing the amount of phosphoric acid in the mixture.

On increasing the amount of thorium nitrate in the gel-forming mixtures, the rate of change in viscosity decreases and the viscosity-time curves (Fig. 2) become less steep. This is due to the fact that thorium ions peptise thorium phosphate and thus increase the degree of dispersity of the micelles. This effect decreases rapid changes in

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

viscosity; it also increases the density of charge on the micelles and thereby diminishes their rate of hydration which again decreases the rate of change in viscosity (*cf.* Dhar, *J. Phys Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1566). From the transparency of all the gels studied herein, it appears that the degree of hydration of the micelles is very great and plays an important part in affecting changes in the viscosity of the gel-forming mixtures.

The addition of non-electrolytes (*cf.* Fig. 5) decreases the rate of change in viscosity. In the earlier stages (for about 15 to 20 minutes) the viscosity of the mixture increases but later on it decreases as the amount of the non-electrolytes in the mixture is increased. The first increase may be due to the formation of bigger particles of the precipitate of thorium phosphate which has a tendency to separate out due to a decrease in its solubility in non-electrolyte-water mixtures, more so as larger quantities of non-electrolytes are added to the mixture. This explanation is supported by the fact that in the case of alcohols and acetone a slight precipitate separated out just after mixing and disappeared after sometime. No such separation of any precipitate was observed in the case of glycol and glycerol.

FIG. 5.

Curves I—III taken from curves in Fig. 1 and IV & VII from those in Fig. 2.

The behaviour of non-electrolytes can be explained on the suggestion of Prasad and Hattiangadi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 991) that non-electrolytes increase the density of charge on positively charged sols. Consequently in accordance with Dhar's views the degree of hydration of colloidal particles decreases and hence the rate of change in viscosity of the gelling system is decreased.

The addition of acids and sodium chloride (*cf.* Fig. 6) increases the rate of change in viscosity with time. This is in agreement with the usual effect of electrolytes that they decrease the density of charge on colloidal particles and thereby the degree of hydration of the particle and the rate of change in viscosity of the gelling system are increased. But it has been found that H-ions are very effective in peptising thorium phosphate. Hence when lower concentrations of the acids are employed, the density of charge on the colloid particles increases and the lowering in the rate of viscosity is observed.